

The first records of *Platycheirus europaeus* (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the central part of European Russia

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Prokhorov, A. V. The first records of *Platycheirus europaeus* (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the central part of European Russia. — The hoverfly *Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990 is collected in Moscow Region and recorded from central part of European Russia for the first time. Distribution is summarized and a comparative diagnosis of this species is given.

Key words: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Platycheirus europaeus*, Russia.

Прохоров, О. В. Перші знахідки *Platycheirus europaeus* (Diptera: Syrphidae) у центральній частині Європейської Росії. — Мухоповисюху *Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990 знайдено у Московській області та вперше відзначено з центральної частини Європейської Росії. Узагальнено відомості про поширення виду та наведено його діагноз.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Platycheirus europaeus*, Росія.

Прохоров, А. В. Первые находки *Platycheirus europaeus* (Diptera: Syrphidae) в центральной части Европейской России. — Мухажурчалка *Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990 поймана в Московской области и впервые отмечена для центральной части Европейской России. Обобщены сведения о распространении вида и дан его диагноз.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Syrphidae, *Platycheirus europaeus*, Россия.

Introduction

A large genus *Platycheirus* Le Peletier & Serville, 1828 is represented in Russia by 74 species (12 of the subgenus *Pachysphyria* and 62 of the subgenus *Platycheirus*) (Barkalov & Mutin, 2018; Prokhorov, 2018). *Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990 is known as widespread species in Palaearctic Region (see Distribution below), although it has not yet been found in some large regions (e. g., in Ukraine). In Russia, the species was recorded from Siberia and Far East (Barkalov & Mutin, 2018). We are unaware of any publications with the data on presence of the species in European Russia. Information about this was found on the site (Polev, 2013), where the species was recorded from Karelia (north of European Russia). Recently, while studying hoverflies in

Tabolovo (Moscow Region), in 2015–2019, *Platycheirus europaeus* was collected for the first time in the central part of European Russia.

Material and methods

The specimens of *P. europaeus* are deposited in I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv).

The morphological terminology follows of Cumming & Wood (2017). Diagnosis is generally based on the keys by Speight & Goeldlin de Tiefenau (1990), Bartsh *et al.* (2009), and Van Veen (2010).

Fig. 1–4. *Platycheirus europaeus*, habitus: 1, 3 — dorsal view (1 — male, 3 — female); 2, 4 — lateral view (2 — male, 4 — female).

Photos of flies are taken using a Canon PowerShot A640 camera mounted on Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000 binocular microscope; all images were subsequently combined with Helicon Focus (version 6.0.18) and processed in Adobe Photoshop CS6 by the author.

***Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990 (figs 1–9)**

Material examined. Russia: Moscow Region, Tabolovo, 55.915N 36.049E, in the garden, 18.08.2015, 1 ♂, 7.06.2019, 1 ♀; Tabolovo env.: 55.9133N 36.0757E, clearing in mixed forest, 20.08.2015, 1 ♂, 4.06.2017, 2 ♂, 10.06.2019, 1 ♀; 55.906097N 36.069301E, glade in mixed forest, 13.06.2016, 1 ♀, 29.05.2017, 4 ♂, 1 ♀; 55.900201N 36.04062E, edge of mixed forest, 14.06.2016, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland; Russia (north of European Territory, Siberia, Far East); Japan (Maibach *et al.*, 1992; Dirickx, 1994; Holinka & Mazánek, 1997; Wolff, 1998; Nielsen, 1999; Reemer, 2000; Stubbs & Falk, 2002; Van de Weyer, 2002; Vujić *et al.*, 2002; Stănescu & Pârnu, 2005; Pakalniškis *et al.*, 2006; De Groot & Govedič, 2008; Karpa, 2008; Bartsh *et al.*, 2009; Reemer *et al.*, 2009; Tóth, 2011, 2014; Williams *et al.*, 2011; Poley, 2013; Haarto & Kerppola, 2014; Ôhara *et al.*, 2014; Ricarte & Marcos-García, 2017; Barkalov & Mutin, 2018; Speight *et al.*, 2018; Speight, 2020; Mielczarek & Żóralski, 2021); central part of European Russia (**first record**).

Diagnosis. *Platycheirus europaeus* belongs to *P. clypeatus* group of species (Speight & Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1990; Bartsh *et al.*, 2009). This group can be recognized from the entirely black antenna, orange-brown markings on the abdominal tergites, facial tubercle and upper mouth-edge projecting anteriorly no further than the frontal prominence, male fore tibia widening progressively from base to apex (Speight & Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1990). Based on the external morphological features, *Platycheirus europaeus* can be often confused with some members of this group: *P. angustatus* (Zetterstedt, 1843), *P. angustipes* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1974, *P. clypeatus* (Meigen, 1822), *P. occultus* Goeldlin, Maibach and Speight, 1990 and *P. ramsarensis* Goeldlin, Maibach & Speight, 1990.

Platycheirus europaeus **male** differs from males of *P. angustipes*, *P. clypeatus* and *P. occultus* by the underside of the first fore tarsomere with a V-shaped pale furrow (in the other species, the underside of the first fore tarsomere with a straight, pale central furrow, sometimes ending in a small round pit containing a black mark). *Platycheirus europaeus* is similar to *P. angustatus* and *P. ramsarensis* in having underside of the first fore tarsomere with a V-shaped pale furrow. It can be separated from *P. angustatus* by the posterior anepisternum covered with microtrichia (in *P. angustatus*, posterior anepisternum shining, without microtrichia), posterior side of fore femur (except for the bent white seta) with only straight macrotrichia (in *P. angustatus*, posterior side of the fore femur with several bent macrotrichia in addition to the bent white seta). *Platycheirus europaeus* differs from *P. ramsarensis* by: V-shaped furrow on underside of the first fore

Fig. 5–9. *Platycheirus europaeus*, details of structure: 5, 6 — male head (5 — anterolateral view, 6 — frontal view); 7 — male tarsus of the fore leg, ventral view; 8 — male fore and mid left legs, anterior view; 9 — female head, anterolateral view.

tarsomere situated in apical half, but near the middle (in *P. ramsarensis*, the V-shaped furrow on underside of the first fore tarsomere is at the tarsomere apex); entire posterior side of the fore femur with macrotrichia (in *P. ramsarensis*, posterior side of the fore femur bare in apical half); the first hind tarsomere not distinctly swollen (in *P. ramsarensis*, the first hind tarsomere distinctly swollen).

Platycheirus europaeus **female** is most similar to females of *P. magadanensis* Mutin, 1999, *P. podagratus* (Zetterstedt, 1838) and *P. ramsarensis* in having the hind femur mainly black, at most narrowly yellow at base. From *P. angustatus* it can be separated by the abdomen broader, tergites square or transverse (in *P. angustatus*, abdomen slender, tergites longer than wide); posterior anepisternum covered with microtrichia (in *P. angustatus*, posterior anepisternum shining, without microtrichia). From *P. ramsarensis* it can be distinguished by: tergite 2 square, or only slightly transverse (in *P. ramsarensis*, tergite 2 distinctly transverse): tarsi of the fore and mid legs entirely yellow (in *P. ramsarensis*, at least couple of tarsomeres of tarsi of the fore and mid legs black); entire

posterior side of the fore femur with macrotrichia (in *P. ramsarensis*, only basal half of posterior side of the fore femur with macrotrichia). *Platycheirus europaeus* female can be separated from *P. podagratus* by the tergite 3 with square spots (in *P. podagratus*, all paired spots on tergites 2–4 round, or spots on tergites 3 and 4 roughly shaped as quarters of a circle); dust spots on frons larger, leaving only the central third shining (in *P. podagratus*, dust spots on frons smaller, leaving the central half shining); tarsomeres 2 and/or 3 of the tarsus of hind leg yellow (in *P. podagratus*, the tarsus of hind leg entirely black). From very similar *P. magadanensis* it differs by the paired spots on tergites 3 and 4 reaching anterior margins (in *P. magadanensis*, paired spots on tergites 3 and 4 not quite reaching their anterior margins); vertex in front of the posterior ocelli distinctly transverse (almost twice as wide as long) (in *P. magadanensis*, vertex in front of the posterior ocelli almost square, less than 1.5 times as wide as long).

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